

LOGBOOK

MBBS

Department of Community Medicine

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LOGBOOK COMMITTEE

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Department of Community Medicine, Govt Medical College Alwar

2025

University Registration No.

University Roll No.

College Roll No.

Name

Batch

Mentor

Guardian

Contact

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Phase 1 : Ist Professional Year

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory / Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory / Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory / Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Self Directed Learning	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Family Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date		Remarks	Sign

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that this is the bonafide record of _____, enrolled in phase ____ from _____ to _____, whose documented entries herein show a progressive and satisfactory acquisition of the required milestones and competencies in Community Medicine as per the Competency-Based Undergraduate Medical Education (CBME) curriculum.

Remarks :

Signature of Mentor

Signature of HOD

Phase 2 : IInd Professional Year

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory / Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory / Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory / Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Self Directed Learning	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Family Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Clinical Postings / Field Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Clinical Postings / Field Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	_____	Remarks	Sign

CERTIFICATE

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Remarks :

Signature of Mentor

Signature of HOD

Phase 3 : IIIrd Professional Year

n.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Theory Classes	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Small Group Teaching / Practical	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Clinical Postings / Field Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Clinical Postings / Field Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Clinical Postings / Field Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Clinical Postings / Field Visits	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Family Visit	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Epidemiological Exercises	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Epidemiological Exercises	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Bio-Statistical Work	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Bio-Statistical Work	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Pandemic Module	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	AETCOM Module Activity	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date		Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	_____	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date		Remarks	Sign

CERTIFICATE

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Remarks :

Signature of Mentor

Signature of HOD

Competencies Completed

Competency	Brief Description	Remarks	Sign
1.9	Demonstrate the role of effective communication skills in health in simulated environment.		
1.10	Demonstrate the important aspects of the doctor patient relationship in a simulated environment		
2.1	Describe the steps and perform clinic-social-cultural and demographic assessment of the individual, family and community		
2.2	Describe the sociology-cultural factors, family(types), its role in health and disease and demonstrate in a simulated environment the correct assessment of socioeconomic status		

2.3	Describe and demonstrate in a simulated environment the assessment burden of barriers to good health and health seeking behavior		
3.1	AETCOM : Demonstrate ability to communicate to patients in a patient respectful non threatening non judgmental and empathetic manner		
3.3	AETCOM : Administer informed consent and appropriately address patient queries to a patient undergoing a surgical procedure in a simulated environment		
4.3	Demonstrate and describe the steps in evaluation of health promotion and education program		
5.2	Describe and demonstrate the correct method of performing a nutritional assessment of individuals, families and the community by using the appropriate method		

5.4	Plan and recommend a suitable diet for the individuals and families based on local availability of foods, economic status in a simulated environment		
6.2	Describe and discuss the principles and demonstrate the methods of collection, classification, analysis, interpretation and presentation of statistical data		
6.3	Describe, discuss and demonstrate the application of elementary statistical methods including test of significance in various study designs		
6.4	Enumerate, discuss and demonstrate common sampling techniques, simple statistical methods frequency distribution measures of central tendency		
7.4	Define, calculate and interpret morbidity and mortality indicators based on given set of data		

7.6	Enumerate and evaluate the need of screening tests		
7.7	Describe and demonstrate the steps in the investigation of an epidemic of communicable diseases and describe principles of control measures		
9.2	Define, calculate and interpret demographic indices including birth rate, death rate and fertility rates		

* Only Show-how competencies listed above.

Non-Core Activities

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Activity Description	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Activity Description	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Activity Description	Remarks	Sign

Sn.	Comp.	Date	Activity Description	Remarks	Sign

Assessment Reports

Family Adoption Program Assessment

Phase 3	Phase 2	Phase 1	Areas assessed*:
			Appearance and general behavior
			Punctuality
			Attitude towards community
			Relationship with other students
			Relationship with people in the community
			Collection of data
			Presentation of data
			Interpretation of data
			Ability to relate finding to solving community health problems
			Student critique of his own approach
			Ability to suggest solutions to problems
			Contribution to group discussion
			Performance in crisis situation
			Assessment of survey report

* (Graded as B/M/E)

Manual Quality

Criterion	Grade*	Sign
Completion		
Quality of Content		
Appropriate diagrams where required		
Neatness		
Overall		

Categorical Assessment of Professionalism

Phase	Areas assessed					Sign
	Punctuality	Coursework	Behavior & Discipline	Knowledge & skills	Overall *	
Phase 1						
Phase 2						
Phase 3						

* (Graded as B/M/E)

Assessment Marks

Sn.	Type of Assessment	Maximum Marks		Obtained Marks		Date	Sign
		Theory	Practical	Theory	Practical		

Assessment Marks

Sn.	Type of Assessment	Maximum Marks		Obtained Marks		Date	Sign
		Theory	Practical	Theory	Practical		

Assessment of the Student

Strengths :

Suggestions :

Mentor Sign :

Summary Report of the Student

Description and Particulars			Sign
	Theory	Practical	
Attendance (%) Total (PY1+PY2+PY3)			
Assessment Total (PY1+PY2+PY3)			
All 18 SH Competencies (Grade : B/M/E)			
	Expected	Completed	
Family Case			
Clinicosocial Case			
Field Visits			
Seminar			
Clinical Postings			
Self-Directed Learning Assessment			
Small Group Discussion Assessment			
Record Maintenance (Grade : B/M/E)			
AETCOM (Grade : B/M/E)			
Investigation of Epidemic (Yes/No)			
Electives in Community Medicine (if any)			
Non-core activities			
Research Undertaken (Yes/No)			
Workshops/ Conferences (Yes/No)			
Co-curricular (Yes/No)			
Volunteering in Department Activities			
Prizes/Awards (if any)			
Overall Assessment			

Family Adoption Program Certificate

This is to certify that _____ (Roll No. ____)
has successfully completed the family adoption program of the village
_____ in the department of Community medicine of
Government Medical College Alwar, Rajasthan and during this period,
his/her work was found to be satisfactory.

Remarks :

Signature of Head of Department

Certificate of Completion

This is to certify that this logbook is the bonafide record of _____ (Roll No. ___) admitted to this course in the academic year _____ from _____ to _____. His/Her log of competencies acquired are as noted in the entries in this logbook in the subject of community medicine and related AETCOM modules as per competency based undergraduate medical education curriculum, during this period his/her work is satisfactory. He/She is considered eligible to appear for the Summative (University) assessment for this course.

Remarks :

Signature of Head of Department

Annexes

Annexure 1

Interpretation of Grading

The logbook uses grading for assessing student's performance and effort during the course as per recommendations in Competency Based Medical Education guidelines by National Medical Commission and recommendation of Indian Association of Preventive and Social Medicine logbook committee. It recognizes that clinical acumen, ability to implement, leadership, empathy,. etc cannot be entirely encapsulated by a single alphanumeric grade, the metrics below only serve as a broad heuristic. They guide faculty in evaluating a student's developmental trajectory across the domains. The ultimate goal is to certify that the student has completed his training in public health towards a capable health advocate, a lifelong learner, and a competent primary care physician. Below tables describe grades and their non-exhaustive interpretation of how competent was the student assessed to be at the completion of course related work or activity or his/her engagement level in the activity based on the type of activity. In the activity sections of the logbook, grade entries are made in the Remarks column along with attempt entries whether the activity, competency or task was successfully accomplished or was suggested to be repeated. In composite graded areas like family adoption program, etc. mathematical mode of all the given grades shall be taken as final grade. In the competencies completed checklist only those competencies having show how component have been mentioned for record and certification out of total set of competencies prescribed by National Medical Commission for this course.

Grading Rubric (B/ M/ E)

This matrix shows the evaluation criteria across domains to provide a picture of student proficiency.

Abbreviations

Grading/ Rating	B	Below Expectations
	M	Meets Expectations
	E	Exceeds Expectations
Attempt at activity by student	F	First attempt only
	R	Repeat attempt
	Re	Remedial attempt
Decision of faculty after attempt	C	Completed
	R	Repeat
	Re	Remedial

Note: In composite evaluations (e.g., Family Adoption Program, etc), the final grade is the mathematical mode of the individual domain scores.

Activity	Exceeds Expectations(E)	Meets Expectations(M)	Below Expectations(B)
SGD Seminars	Initiates & drives with thorough preparation & critical analysis with advanced public health reasoning, demonstrates leadership & facilitates group consensus.	Active & prepared participant contributing relevant public health knowledge with near adequate grasp and keen to learn more.	Passive with minimal effort with little contribution to discussion, Dominates the conversation without facilitating collaborative learning .
Clinicosocial Cases	Explains social determinants of health, proposes highly practical, realistic, community-tailored interventions.	Collects accurate history and data. Identifies standard public health problems and suggests standard, textbook-appropriate interventions.	Focuses exclusively on biomedical diagnosis, misses key social determinants, proposes interventions that are impractical or ignore ground patient's reality
Family Adoption	Builds exceptional rapport. Demonstrates high empathy and cultural sensitivity. Interprets family health data deeply and anticipates crisis scenarios proactively.	Maintains a respectful, professional relationship with the family , Collects data and relates findings to common health problems.	Poor punctuality or unprofessional behavior , doesn't show professional neutrality. Fails to build trust. Data collection is superficial; unable to suggest viable health solutions.
Field Visits	Demonstrates exceptional situational awareness. Critically analyzes the health system's workflow, identifies systemic gaps, and interacts with community members and allied health workers with deep cultural sensitivity.	Professional and engaged. Interacts respectfully with healthcare workers and the community. Accurately records observations and understands the facility's specific role within the healthcare tier.	Disengaged or lacks professionalism , Fails to grasp the functional dynamics of the health facility or shows a lack of appropriate rapport.
Practicals Exercises	Anticipates requirements & executes tasks independently, integrates epidemiological theory with practical task at hand, content utilizes high-quality, relevant diagrams and critical insights beyond basics.	Complete, legible, and submitted on time. Content is accurate with accurate procedures, clinically sound, and includes the required diagrams and observations.	Incomplete or frequently late. Lacks required diagrams, shows poor attention to detail, struggles to connect practical step with underlying public health concepts.
Overall Misc	Exemplary discipline. Consistently punctual, demonstrates a high standard of medical ethics, and actively seeks out feedback for self-improvement.	Reliable punctuality and appropriate classroom/Posting behavior. Follows ethical guidelines and respects faculty and peers.	Frequently tardy or absent. Exhibits disruptive behavior or poor professional boundaries. Resistant to faculty feedback.

Annexure 2

Guidelines for Students

General Guidelines : This logbook is structured into three phases per the Competency-Based Medical Education (CBME) curriculum. Entries must be recorded in chronological order within their respective phases. Students are required to log their coursework regularly for faculty remarks and signatures. If faculty require an activity to be repeated, it must be logged de-novo on the actual date of repetition. Any other tasks advised during the course should be recorded in the Miscellaneous section. Self-directed learning must be student-initiated and duly documented. Final logbook submission for grading occurs after the completion of the required manual(s) and other requirements as indicated.

Non-Core activity : Although not compulsory, participating in non-core activities is highly encouraged to further augment core clinical and public health competencies. Recommended engagements include research, statistical analyses, academic quizzes (e.g., IAPSM World Health Day Quiz), field task volunteering, attending or presenting at workshops, health-promoting extracurricular like sports and yoga, .etc.

Recommended Sources : Core texts include Park's Textbook of Preventive and Social Medicine. References: Epidemiology by Leon Gordis, General Practice by G Vaidya, Oxford Textbook of Public Health and Learning Stats with Jamovi.